

**TEACHING ENGLISH TO SCHOOL STUDENTS AND THE
IMPORTANCE OF APPLICATION****Pirmatova Kamola Abdigapurovna**

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Abstract: In this article, interactive methods and methods of their use in the course of the lesson are highlighted, and the importance of interactive methods is discussed in the teaching of English. Therefore, information about the convenience of these methods in mastering a foreign language was also given.

Key words: interactive method, English language, effective teaching, education, student, foreign language, importance.

INTRODUCTION

We know that at the meeting of the video selector dedicated to the improvement of the foreign language teaching system chaired by our president Shavkat Mirziyoyev, it was emphasized that from 2021 foreign language teachers will be required to have national and international certificates. This puts a huge responsibility on the shoulders of our foreign language teachers. Now, instead of traditional teaching methods, we should organize the teaching process based on interactive methods using new information technologies. It should be noted that new methods and requirements have been developed in our country for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers in accordance with the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). According to it, textbooks are being created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, the classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language has also increased day by day. The subject of a foreign language is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening and speaking), and specific concepts and skills are given for each of them.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

foreign language teaching as a science has more than 200 years of history. During this period, it can be observed that different attitudes towards foreign language teaching methodology were expressed. Academician L. V. Shcherba belongs to one of these views. In his opinion, although the methodology of teaching any science is a science, it is not considered a theoretical science. It

solves practical problems. In particular, the foreign language teaching methodology does not rely only on psychological evidence, but is based on general and specific linguistic studies. If linguistics deals with the origin and laws of movement of language phenomena, the methodology answers the question of what should be done in order to use the necessary language phenomenon in practice based on these laws.

The most valuable books on methodology are also written by linguists. These include G. Suit, one of the 19th century phoneticians and a great English linguist, O. Yespersen, who was considered the most original phonetician and theoretical linguist in England at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries, and one of the most prominent French linguists in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, F. Bryuns and Brealya, prominent anglicist and famous phonetician V. Fyotor and others.

Academician LVShcherba and his mentor, the great linguist IABoduen-deCourtone and their students dealt with the issue of language teaching methodology in Russia. Psychologists had a different attitude to the methodology of foreign language teaching. Professor VA Artemov made a valuable comment about the relationship between methodology and psychology. In his opinion, psychology provides material for methodology. Methodology studies how the teacher conducts the lesson. Psychology deals with how students learn this subject. However, one cannot fully agree with this opinion. Because the teacher in the process of teaching, and the student in the period of mastering experience certain mental processes and states, whether they want to or not, they face and are influenced by the laws of psychology.

teaching and learning a foreign language (English) is very effective. *In particular:*

- ✓ when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language video clips, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons;
- ✓ it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs;
- ✓ the use of tape recorders and cassettes, which is considered a more traditional method;
- ✓ CD players are available. Here, students are given ample opportunities to develop their communicative competence in a foreign language.

First of all, the learner hears several variants of the pronunciation process of words and thereby forms his own pronunciation skills. *Secondly*, the student who observes the communication process of the communicators through the image will witness the non-verbal actions of the communicators, through which

strategic competence will be formed in the student. *Thirdly*, they get to know the culture of representatives of a foreign language through the image, which encourages the formation of the learner's sociolinguistic competence. *Fourthly*, it is possible to hear and repeat the information transmitted through these technologies, which means that the students have the opportunity to *re* - learn the areas they do not understand, either by themselves or with a group. The above- mentioned circumstances make the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students.

Modern education requires the use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, communicative and informational tools.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted process, in which a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing a foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are: communicative didactic method, intercultural dialogue organization method and exercise organization method.

In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, they have a high demand for language learning. Currently, foreign languages are taught in schools, colleges, lyceums, and higher education institutions. There are innovative types of learning materials for those who want to have different levels of language knowledge. Perfect knowledge of a foreign language and obtaining a certain degree also depends on the practical methods and qualifications of teachers. The ability to use information technology and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials.

By combining different methods, the teacher is able to solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the ability to choose the most effective methods to achieve their goals is formed. In this case,

using several methods of teaching and learning will be effective. As time progresses, there is more and more innovation in every field.

Advanced methods serve as a compound in the thorough mastery of a foreign language.

One such method is the use of role - playing games in the teaching process. Role-playing games are the application of different situations in our real life in the process of learning a foreign language. This method helps to create a language environment in the course of the lesson.

In the process of participating in role-playing games, students learn to think, learn to freely express their emotional states in a foreign language. In the process of preparing for role- playing games, they correct each other's lexical, grammatical and pronunciation mistakes . Making mistakes and correcting them also helps language learning and teaches students correct pronunciation. The use of role-playing games in the course of the lesson ensures that all students are actively involved in the lesson at the same time. In addition, role-playing games increase students' interest in learning a foreign language and create a lively, fun atmosphere for the learning process. This serves to increase the effectiveness of foreign language lessons.

The next method is " Case study ". in English, ("case " - specific situation, event, " study " - study, analyze) is a method aimed at teaching based on the study and analysis of specific situations.

One of the most interesting methods is " Pantomimo ". The game is divided into 3 groups. One person from each group is put on the board. They are given different words based on the list. They have to explain the words to the rest of the group through gestures and actions without saying a word.

Creative Problem Solving (Creative Problem Solving) is used to read the beginning of the story and let the students decide how it ends;

Merry Riddles Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to a riddle;

Quick answers help improve the effectiveness of the lesson;

- Chigil wrote (Warm-up exercises) using various games in the classroom to make students interested in the lesson;

- Pantomime (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are done and students are tired;

- A chain story method helps students to develop oral speech;

Role-playing games (Acting characters), this method can be used in all types of lessons.

- ❖ To teach a trade
- ❖ Interpreter,
- ❖ Translator,
- ❖ Writer,
- ❖ Professionals such as poets can participate in class and talk to students;
 - ✦ Poets and writers can be invited to Thinkers meeting. At such a time, using the words of wisdom they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people;
 - ✦ Pictures the When pictures speak method is very convenient and helps to teach English and develop the oral speech of students, for this it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic;
 - ✦ Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time.

seen, each innovative technology has its own advantages. In all such methods, cooperation between the teacher and the student, the active action of the student in the educational process is envisaged.

CONCLUSION

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to answer quickly and correctly is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies. possible

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